

ATTITUDE TOWARDS YOGA OF HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS WITH RESPECT TO TYPE OF SCHOOL

Miss. R. Chinnathai

M.Ed. Student, S Veerasamy Chettiar College of Education, Puliangudi – 627855

Dr. N. Subramanian

Assistant Professor, S Veerasamy Chettiar College of Education, Puliangudi – 627855

ABSTRACT

The main aim of the present study is to find out significant difference in attitude towards yoga of high school students with respect to type of school. The investigator used the survey method of research. The investigator used the Attitude towards Yoga Scale (2016). It is a self-made tool which is standardized and validated by the investigator. The sample for present study consists of 300 high school students from 10 schools of Sivagiri Taluk selected by random sampling method. The investigator used mean, standard deviation and F-test for descriptive analysis and inferential analysis. From the result of inferential analysis, the investigator found that there is no significant difference in attitude toward yoga of high school students with respect to type of school.

KEYWORDS : Yoga, high school students, F-test, Inferential Analysis, Descriptive Analysis

INTRODUCTION

According to Sri Aurobindo, "Yoga is the way or method through which internal and external facilities of man meets in totality and changes occur and by which may achieve God or feel his existence and may be one the part of him". Yoga is very ancient discipline. It is recognized as one of the most important and valuable gifts of our heritage. Today the world is looking of Yoga for solving the various problems faced by humanity. At no time in the past Yoga had attracted so much of attention from people around so many places in the world as it is today. In spite of this fact, no field is so miserably misunderstood as yoga in India. If one takes a cross section of society and makes a general survey on the public opinion about yoga, many misconceptions about yoga may surface out. The main aim of yoga is integrating the body, mind, and thoughts so as work for good ends. Modern life style leads to diseases, which are mostly due to poor food habits, heavy daily routines and to air and water pollution in turn easily affect the human body. The human mind is just like a fire. It could be either used to preserve and to destroy. With a matchstick one can light a candle and illuminate the house. Yoga was originated in India during ancient time by the yogis. Yoga word is originated from the Sanskrit language and has two meanings, one is union and another one is discipline. Practicing yoga teaches us about the body and mind discipline by uniting or connecting both body and mind. It is a spiritual practice used to meditate in the early morning to balance body and mind as well as remains close to the nature. It was practiced earlier by the people of religions like Hindu, Buddha and Jain. It is amazing type of exercise which makes life better by controlling the body and mind. Yoga is a science of living healthy life forever. It is like a medicine which treats various diseases gradually by regularizing the functioning of body organs.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Yoga is a 5000 year old science whose teachings were first imparted not in a classroom or Gurukul, but on the battle field. In the epic Mahabharata. The Sage, Lord Krishna is first said to have imparted the teachings of yoga to his despondent student Arjuna. Around 1500 years later, another sage, patanjali went on to enunciate, for the benefit of humankind and eternity. They the way to reach the enlightenment of life through a 5 eries of 195 aphorisms (Sutras) in his epic treatise the yoga sutras of patanjali. Derided from the Sanskrit root "Yujir Yogey" meaning to unite, to yoke, to joint to put together. Yoga is about developing harmony between them. In yoga, one will use the mind to diagnose and heal the baby. Yoga is a way of life, a conscious act, not a set or series of learning principles. The dexterity, grace, and noise one cultivates, as a matter of course, is the natural outcome of regular practice. Subsequently, and interestingly, the therapeutic effect of yoga is the direct result of involving the mind totally in inspiring (breathing) the baby to awaken. Today's students face tremendous pressure to achieve within a world that is often overwhelming. The tools of yoga and

mindfulness offer proven methods of developing the inner resilience needed to navigate physical, mental and emotional stress. Bringing these yoga practices to high school students is a simple way to support making students' lives healthier, and can increase their capacity to learn effectively, manage challenging emotions, self-regulate behavior, and achieve personal and academic success. Nowadays, the schools give more importance to yoga practices along with physical education. So the investigator wants to study the attitude towards yoga of high school students with regard to type of school.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To find out the level of attitude towards yoga of high school students with respect to type of school.
- To find out whether there is any significant difference in attitude towards yoga of high school students with respect to type of school.

METHOD OF RESEARCH USED

The investigator used the survey method of research to study the attitude towards yoga of high school students with respect to type of school.

TOOLS USED

Attitude towards Yoga Scale: It is a self-made tool which is standardized and validated by the investigator.

POPULATION OF THE STUDY

The population of the study consists of high school students in the schools of Sivagiri taluk.

SAMPLE OF THE STUDY

The sample for present study consists of 300 high school students from 10 schools of Sivagiri Taluk selected by random sampling method.

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUES USED

Mean, Standard Deviation and F-test

DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS OF DATA

To find out the level of attitude towards yoga of high school students to types of school.

Table - 1 The level of attitude towards yoga of high school students with regard to types of school

Variable	Type of school	Low		Average		High	
		Count	%	Count	%	Count	%
Attitude towards Yoga	Government	30	49.2	14	23.0	17	27.9
	Govt. aided	91	49.2	65	35.1	29	15.7
	Self-finance	33	61.1	19	35.2	2	3.7

It is inferred from the above table that, with regard to government schools, 49.2% of high school students have low level, 23.0% of them have average level and 27.9% of them have high level of attitude towards yoga. With regard government aided schools, 49.2% of high school students have low level, 35.1% of them have average level and 15.7% of them have high level of attitude towards yoga. With regard to self-finance schools, 61.1% of high school students have low level, 35.2% of them have average level and 3.7% of them have high level attitude towards yoga.

H0 1: There is no significant difference in attitude towards yoga of high school students with respect to type of school.

Table - 1 ANOVA showing the significant difference in attitude towards yoga of high school students with respect to type of school

Variable	Type of school	Sum of squares	Df	Mean Square	Calculated 'F' value	Tabulated 'F' value
Attitude towards Yoga	Between Groups	509.724	2	254.862	2.230	3.00
	within groups	33947	297	111.302		

It is inferred from the above table that the calculated t-value (2.230) is less than the table value (3.00) for different (2,297) at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted. It shows that there is no significant difference in attitude toward yoga of high school students with respect to type of school.

FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION

From the result of descriptive analysis of data, the investigator found that more than 49% of government, government aided and self-financed school students have low level of attitude towards yoga. From the result of inferential analysis, the investigator also found that there is no significant difference in attitude toward yoga of high school students with respect to type of school. So it was concluded that the background variable namely type of family have no effect on attitude towards yoga of high school students. Elders of the high school students are responsible for this. Indians which is in middle and poor class no time to think about health. They have issue of filling stomach and how to run family. And also the families are shrinking with less number of members between three and four. Most of the children have lost the opportunity to see their great grand parents or grandparents who could have imparted many ancient art of living and values. Yoga gurus are shrinking in number. And also the present education system lacks a true knowledge and the right kind of individuals who can define educational principles that are good for all humanity. Yoga is a science of education which is not dependent on the mutable conditions of time, space and circumstances or any such objects. It is 'sarvabhauma' having universal standards of self education based, not on changing objects and conditions of happiness, but on habituation to happiness by conditioning the attitudes. Education must only tackle the subconscious and unconscious level it must also be geared to the "subliminal unconsciousness". If Yoga education is to succeed, it will have to battle this subliminal unconscious, and shift away the garbage of the mind to create in the individual the conviction for his growth, peace and happiness. Unless the individual is transformed by the process of Yoga education, how can any society respond positively and manage the changes that occur every day. Despite all the civilization of eras past, a savage heart still beats in man- the animal still remains. Only our concept of him has changed. The animal remains because the usual process of objective and mechanized education of the conscious mind cannot change. The subliminal unconscious Yoga brings about the essential permanent change in the structure of the potencies or in the gens structure, at a deeper level by directing its effects through constant habituation on all planes of consciousness. The Tamil Nadu government on February 2017 announced that it is considering and introducing Yoga in schools, particularly in rural areas. "The government is holding discussions with yoga experts, as students need not only education, but extra-curricular activities like yoga."

REFERENCES

1. Chandra. (2005). Indian Education - Developmental problems, issues and trends. Meerut: Suya Publications.
2. Jeyaprakash. (2007). Research Methodology. New Delhi: APH Publishing Corporation.
3. <http://www.indiacelebrating.com/essay/yoga-essay/>
4. <http://ezinearticles.com/?Yoga-and-Learning-Disabilities&id=363339>
5. <http://www.hvk.org/articles/0706/31.html>